

Influence of Women College Teacher's Employment on Family Life in District Poonch Azad Jammu and Kashmir

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Abstract

This research was an exploration of the influence of women's employment on family life. Working is the best recreation for human beings because of adverse physical, social and psychological motivations; it has adverse effects on family relationships and the quality of life for individuals. The central focus of this study was the effects employed women's have on their families in terms of; economic contribution to household budget. This study plays an important contribution to sociology of work and family. The findings highlight that women in contemporary AJK are playing an important role in enhancing their lives and improving their families' circumstances. An interesting finding is that despite living in male dominated society the women felt empowered due to their employment status. The qualitative methodology was used to collect empirical data.

Keywords: psychological motivations, recreation, family relationships, cotemporary

1. Introduction

Employment is necessary for everyone for their prosperity and consolation. It provides support and improves the quality of life, not just of the employee, but the related people too. It also leads to economic growth and human resource development, either by men or by women. Since the advent of human race, women have been engaged in economic activities to make their families' living standard better, although their efforts have been greatly undermined (Sarwar & Abbasi, 2013). With the passage of time, however, with industrial development, the conditions in urban and rural areas have started changing quite speedily. These days the female members of family are progressively indulged in activities outside home that are economically beneficial for them, which not only makes them independent from financial point of view but they also become strong and empowered socially (Mohyuddin et al., 2012).

Males and females are pillars of society; no society can progress adequately without their equal involvement in all areas of life. With regard to women capabilities, they are no less than men. Women have been involved in socio-economic life equally with men since the Stone Age, but the women's participation in economic activities has not been given the same consideration as men's work. There have been certain forces, social customs and religious taboos that prevented a large number of women's labour flows from seeking employment. These constraints weakened day by day and the overall attitude is becoming more and more helpful (Gupta, 1999).

With time women's role has changed, they now enjoy prominent positions in all areas and departments of life and can't be named just as a housekeeper; they are no less than men in any field and fulfil their duties both at home and workplace. Women are moving shoulders to shoulders with men. Women's economic contribution means the goods and services a woman provides for the survival of her family from the earnings she earns from work outside the home. Women's income could be used to meet the needs of their families and to enhance the living standard of their families and improve their quality of life (Begum & Chakraborty, 1995).

Women have gradually begun to participate in outdoor economic activities, working throughout the world in formal and informal sectors that not only make them financially independent but socially empowered as well (Mohyuddin et al., 2012). The contribution and participation of women in economic activities indicated improved care, food, health and housing (Masika & Joeke, 1996).

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The breadwinner role is traditionally assigned to the males and household work is assigned to females. Society is something dynamic so social ideas and concepts also cannot be static, they too are dynamic. With the passage of time role of women have changed, they are no way lesser than men in any field and fulfilling their duties both at work place and homes. Therefore, today's working women are making a double shift, which consists of taking care of the house, the husband, the children and in-laws, and the work for which they receive the wages outside the boundaries of their housewives duties.

However, current research was particularly focused on the influence of women's employment on family life. Role of employed women in their families in terms of their economic contribution in their families' was the central theme of exploration.

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1.2. Research Objectives

The study was guided by the following objectives:

- To probe the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents.
- To dig out influence of women's employment on family life in terms of economic contribution to household budget

2. Review of Literature

Literature review is sum up for all the publications done by scholars and researchers focussing on some most advanced topics and comparing with previous work. Many of its applications urge the researchers to work on some particular topics which are mostly relevant to high quality articles and upgraded studies which are helpful to sketch them into a complete report. Review of literature aids the researcher to take keen interest and have complete understandings of the research topic, specifically define the domain of the research, clarifying the methodology and accommodating in development of tools (Akbar, 2016).

There is a wide range of middle-class males and females in Pakistan, resulting in low overall support rates contrasting with different nations. Working women are currently participating as a work force, mirroring the socio-social weights of the nation to demoralize working women from allowing their vocation goals to take control of their essential duties as wives and mothers. In Pakistan's rural society, women are primarily responsible for various responsibilities such as daily routine work, farming, child-rearing (Mohyuddin et al., 2012).

After the initiation of NGOs in Pakistan's rural areas, females are given all fundamental abilities, funds and opportunities to work outside their households and receive a wage and enhance their living standards. Because of their involvement, the presence of NGOs in rural regions has demonstrated useful in educating them to enhance their economic abilities and concerns (Butt et al. 2010).

Khan and Khan (2007) presented women's contribution characteristics in the family budget. The findings indicated that the education of females, their ownership of assets and females as heads of the household all have a favorable impact on their participation. The study disclosed that married females contributed more to the household expenditure in informal employment. Woman's age does not affect her contribution.

Azid et al. (2001) estimated by collecting the primary data set the degree of female participation in Pakistan's cottage industry. Study showed that most women involved in the cottage industry in Multan are demonstrating their best in the business of embroidery. Because of poverty, women in Pakistan are involved in many financial activities in every sector. Negative implications are that competition and Purdah function as an obstacle to women involvement in the workplace.

Thomas (1990) examined through his study that income in a mother's hands has a greater impact on family well-being rather than father control. In a Thomas (1993) concluded that women's income is spent on human capital such as health, education, and household facilities and away from home food and meals.

Hoddinott and Haddad (1995) researched the distinct effects of women's revenue contributions on multiple family spending products. Study found that raising the wife's percentage of revenue increased the share of meal spending and reduced the alcohol and cigarette budget size. The same research situation found that women income shares are strongly linked to masculine children's anthropometric rank and do not influence woman children's height-for-age scores (Haddad & Hoddinot, 1994).

Qian (2008) states that it is essential to boost the revenue of women for the preservation of the development percentage of women and to keep the revenue of men steady otherwise vice versa does not guarantee the preservation of women. In many urban regions of India, it is noted that if women lend, they used to invest on woman kids while males lend only for masculine kids (Agier et al., 2012). There is significant proof that women's possession of property leads to increased returns to next-generation welfare through investment in hygiene, education, and clothing for children (Quisumbing & Maluccio, 2000; Doss, 2006).

Khan and Khan (2008) measured the number of females fighting for household preservation in the informal urban industry. Women as head of household, women's education and women's possession of property, family age, household poverty, women's marital status, females residing in nuclear families, and household credits have been discovered to have a beneficial impact on women's contribution to their household budget. The research found that the input rises first and then reduces due to the rise in age of the woman. The number of adult male in the family, however, had decreased the number of women's input. Husband's employment position would be a critical variable for a woman's household budget input.

Naila and Simeen (2009) investigated the poverty consequences of women's jobs in Pakistan's clothing sector by contrasting women's socio-economic limitations, salaries and operating circumstances, and commitment to women's household budget. This article analyses the development of Bangladesh's ready-made garment industry with incentive to boost imports to the country and provide employment possibilities for females. At current, 1.5 million employees

are employed by these sectors, most of whom are females. Women working in these sectors have a beneficial effect on poverty reduction.

Mohammad et al. (2001) focused on the phenomenon of women's financial exercise and jobs. The study was carried out in metropolitan regions of Iran using information on family revenue and expense to assess the position of women in financial exercise. Results from the logistic model have shown that females are more effective than males in handling family spending.

Harkness (2010) analyzed the contribution to household income inequality of employment of and earnings. The research found that increasing women's jobs and earnings for all countries and decreasing women's job inequality would have a important effect on decreasing family income inequality. Women's profits were a major consideration in decreasing family income inequality. Women's earnings have been a major factor in reducing inequality in household income across all countries.

Although married women's employment rates have considerably risen in most industrialized societies, their position in the labor market still leaves them a financial insignificant position. A comparatively elevated proportion of woman workers are part-time engaged, although on median women's profits are considerably smaller in full-time jobs than men's (Blau & Kahn, 1995).

Women's education is on the increase, and over time their job possibilities are improving. Because females with elevated salary opportunities prefer to leave males with excellent business roles (for the evolving system of marriage choice, Oppenheimer, 1988), the proportion of families with two extremely compensated couples is probable to increase. At the other end, unemployment is often determined by organizational factors (i.e. work prospects differ across populations) and high-unemployment households, high-poverty regions face an enhanced danger of both spouses being unemployed (Graaf & Ultee, 2000; Eggers & Massey, 1991). As a consequence, with the increase in (specific) jobs for married females, income inequality and therefore poverty levels would be expected to rise. Cancian and Reed (1999) discovered that while there is a favorable female choice in paid jobs in the U.S. over the previous two centuries have decreased household income inequality compared to the rate it would attain.

A few surveys have tried to employ females professionally (Azid et al., 2001; Khattak & Sayeed, 2000; Sayeed et al., 2002; La Ferrara, 2002). The surveys that analyze serving females concentrate primarily on their revenue, salaries, operating circumstances, advertising system and working hours. Her household rank is determined by the input of women to household revenue (Ramchandran et al., 2001). It takes the family out of poverty and improves the negotiating authority that contributes to family well-being households and kids (Malik & Khan, 2009).

One of the key features of the informal sector is the intensive absorption of children and women on the informal labor market. According to the labor force study, 63% of all working females are involved in Pakistan's informal sector, 60.7% of urban and 65.7 of rural areas (FBS, 2003).

Segregating these women's contribution to their micro-level household budget and to the macro-level informal economy is extremely difficult. Efforts in this direction must be pursued. For at least three reasons, women's contribution in both the budget of households and the informal sector economy remains underestimated. 1. They participate in informal activities that are most challenging to capture and measure, which can be home-based work, contract or piece-rate work, work in household enterprises, and street sales (an extension of an unmeasured or unregistered production activity). 2. more than men, women are engaged in second or multiple jobs, and this phenomenon's failure to measure is a source of underestimation. Their contribution to household production is also greatly underestimated in the presence of their major activities. 3. Women favour such work that has flexible hours, higher consistency with family duties, and relatively easy entry mainly confined within four home walls.

3. Methodological Design

The study was carried out under the methodology of qualitative research in district Poonch AJK. Researcher was interested in qualitative methodology because her ontological and epistemological stance was interpretivist. A sample of 17 married working women was taken as per judgement of researcher because number of married working women was limited. The researcher employed purposive sampling in proposed study.

3.1. Data Collection

The data was gathered from respondents belonging to the profession of teaching, with the help of the interview guide. An interview guide is a collection of questions asked in face-to-face interaction from the respondents.

3.2. Inclusion & Exclusion Criteria

Present study excluded unmarried and non-working women as primary interest of researcher was to find out influence of married working women of the age category of 25-40 years.

4. Analysis

The gathered data was analyzed through the thematic analysis of the qualitative method. Codes were assigned to similar interviewee responses. This enabled the researcher to recognize differences and similarities in the perception of the respondents in respect of specific aspect of a phenomenon being investigated. I put together similar responses and derived themes from them. This helped me to get similar responses to themes.

4.1. Data Analysis and Discussion

Drawing the interviews with the participants, this section shows influence that 'employed women have on their families' in the locale of the study. The research has examined that women's employment have a great influence on their families, in the District Poonch AJK.

Several working women were interviewed as a part of this research. They were asked about how they spend their salaries and what differences their salaries have made in their lives. They co-operated and participated readily.

The first interviewee stated, *"I carry out 70% of the grocery and I don't depend on anyone. When I get salary I go to market myself and buy all the necessary household items that are to be consumed over a period of one month. In addition, to that I buy stuff that children desire to take to school as lunch."* The respondent went on explaining *"I think working women are egoistic. They don't expect from anybody to buy something for them and to fulfil their needs. Working women want to buy all the things that are affordable to them, by themselves"*.

Excerpt indicates that, unlike the common perception that they (women) are economically dependent on their male counterparts; women are the breadwinner in many families. Working women feel much more empowered, they haven't got financial support, they don't waste their knowledge and skills, and they contribute to family improvement. Earnings of women are essential for family life, they are considered to be the great human resource in improving the quality of life. Through income-generating activities, women make a substantial contribution to the family budget. Even though a woman is not entirely alone earning hand, her input to the expenditures is of paramount importance to the family, especially as women spend a great amount of their income on household welfare. Access of women to the cash economy has contributed to household' improved economic status.

Yet another interviewee explained throwing light on the query, *"With the salary of my husband our basic needs were fulfilled but we had no luxurious items in our house. We used to live in a village where there were no facilities, for example, no good school which could provide quality education. Even there were no paved roads. After starting job, I tend to use my income on items of luxury. I rented a house in urban area and now I pay the rent of the house myself. We are residing there, so the standard of my family could improve. As urban area provides all the facilities this allows my family to enjoy a wonderful life with all the facilities."*

This excerpt shows that working women are not only trying to provide their families with basic facilities, but also trying to improve their families' living standard. Women's employment leads to improved care, nutrition and housing for the family. This ultimately leads to household members' well-being.

In response to question regarding, how employed women spend their earning and savings, most of the respondents argued, they had financial savings. Some of them saved, but the earnings were very tiny, and their money were usually invested on the family's daily expenditures. Few respondents were having savings which they spent on buying on the major items for their homes.

One of the participants shared that she was living away from her husband for the sake of improving their standard of life. She said, *"I recently got a job. I have been appointed in a college in another city. I have been living with my children in a rented house. I bear the expenses of rent and transportation from my own salary. Children are living with me, so I spend on their needs as well. I don't get money from my husband therefore; I don't get to save money."*

This excerpt shows that, women are eventually empowered by participation in economic activities. They do not rely on others, even their husband. The women who work may provide their families with better future. Financially independent women are able to make their own decisions and need not to depend on anyone. This increases their self-respect and makes them more confident in dealing with any kind of life situations.

On a query about earnings and savings another interviewee expressed her desires and shared, *"I bought a car and a plot, from my savings. I want to build another house despite having one house presently and for that I have participated in committee so that I could build another house"*. On probing the question that why she is interested in two houses, the respondent went on describing that she desired to have two houses because she had two sons and she wanted to build them a house from her income".

This excerpt proves that employed women not only fulfil the basic mundane needs but also spend in order to secure the future of their children.

One of the interviewee expressed how her employment has made her self sufficient and how she reduces her husband's burden, she responded, *"I have kept my husband entirely relaxed. I have an out of station job. So I live along with my children in a hostel, do job and study as well. My children go to school. I bear all the expenses of my education, my children's education and daily basic needs. I never demand money from my husband. He himself gives*

whatever and whenever he desires. I have not bound my husband. I have a satisfactory income and I can easily afford everything."

For money or anything else, a working woman does not need to depend on husband. Without relying on husband, she becomes independent and earns her own. Without being accountable to anyone in the family, she can fulfil all her desires and needs.

One of the respondents explicated " *I am living in a joint family system. My husband and I have divided our income. I spend my income on myself and on my children, whereas my husband spends his income on the rest of the family members like his father, mother and siblings; he is supporting them."*

Working women are becoming more cooperative and efficient in the modern era as needs are growing. They share the burden of their husbands. During discussion, women who were working in non-government institutions stated that they are working in more than one institution at a time to reduce their husbands' burden.

In response to question regarding job's reasons, some of the participants told that to give good education to their kids, it was indispensable for them to work. They responded in the way, "*We are working to give good education to our children so they could attend good schools. Education is getting expensive by each passing day, so it is highly unavoidable for both man and woman to work. They should be able to give good education to their children along with daily mundane expenses. When both husband and wife work, only then the needs of the house will be fulfilled, and children will also study in well reputed schools.*

The excerpt depicts that, women are moving with men shoulder to shoulder. Women work for poverty reduction and the fulfilment of needs. As inflation rate increase, women continue to be engaged in economic activities, so that they could financially sustain their families, provide their kids with education and a better future.

Another interviewee shared how her employment is grooming her and how it's a source of learning for her. She said, "*I am educated and I don't want to waste my education by sitting idle in the house, and I am working because I like to work. I have no compulsion to work. I am working so that I can transfer knowledge to the generations to come and secondly because I want to groom myself. I think that the syllabus that is being taught now a days is very informative and detailed and I am also learning new approaches owing to present day designs."*

This excerpt indicates that education is one of the main determinants of women's entry into the labour market. Human capital Investment such as experience and on- the job training improves productivity, leading to greater employment income. Not only because of financial security, but also because they have a desire to share their knowledge, women are currently working.

5. Conclusion

Women of present era are no way lesser than men. Working women consume much of their income on household related expenditures. They are capable of sharing all the responsibilities of life. So no one can ignore their sacrifices for their families by doing both jobs inside their homes and outside. In the present era, the participation of women in earnings and economic activities to contribute to their household budget has become vital and necessary. Due to high inflation rate, conversion of luxuries into necessities, high expenditure on education and health of children, the household expenditures have been increased. So, instead of distinguished domains of both partners it became mandatory to be co-operative and run the vehicle of life, being two tires of vehicle. So, instead of negative impact, employment of married women has positive impact on families. So, the current research was an attempt to probe the idea in practical way.

5.1. Recommendations

It is indicated that most of the working women contribute to the household budget due to unmet household budget stress. They are struggling for families' survival. Thus an increase in employed women's income and productivity may have trickle down effects on reduction of the poverty of household and burden on women. Following recommendations are made to increase the women's contribution in employment.

- Government should provide women permanent jobs with more friendly and pleasant policies, as they are more supportive and loyal to their families.
- Policies should work on improving women's education with a view to improving productivity and efficiency and promoting poverty reduction in households.
- Government should also ensure that childcare facilities are provided with subsidies. The mothers can relax from childcare responsibilities and can actively participate in outdoor economic activities and increase their contribution in the budget of household in this way.

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